

Implementations of Teaching Arabic: Role Play Strategy as a Case Study

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
October 29, 2020

Accepted:
December 31, 2020

Keywords

Role-Playing, Reading,
Arabic Language

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4408538

Abstract

This paper aims to identify the impact of the application of role-play strategy in teaching Arabic. With this regard, "reading" is selected to be the considered sample of language skills, by virtue of covering a population that consists of second-grade students in a school in Abu Dhabi. The problematic of this study is set in the objective of answering the following research questions: What results does the application of role-play on the reading skill, in Arabic language, have on young learners? Are there any statistically significant differences regarding the experimental group which applied the role-play method, on the one hand, and the score average of the control group which received the traditional learning method in the contemplative thinking test, on the other hand? Are there statistically significant differences at the high achievement level in the experimental group and the mean scores of their peers in the control group in the contemplative thinking test? Geared toward answering the above research questions, role play strategy is applied to second primary class students, which are divided into two streams, each comprising 28 male and female learners. Moreover, a well defined study unit is selected, for the purpose of obtaining the best possible results. Accordingly, the contemplative test covers the basic language skills, and these are: Observation, developing proposed solutions, interpretation, conclusion, and disclosure of fallacies. Once the post test is concluded, the results reveal that there are statistically significant differences in favor of the experimental group. There appear to be statistically significant differences in all dimensions of the reflective thinking test, and the overall score of high achievers in both experimental and control groups. The results, eventually, are in favor of high achievers in the experimental group. Furthermore, there appear to be statistically significant differences in all dimensions of the contemplative thinking test, and the overall score between the high achievers in both experimental and control groups. However, the results were in favor of low Achievers in the experimental group. The results are interpreted in the light of the theoretical framework in addition to the results of previous studies. Hence, the study recommends benefiting from the role-play method in various branches of the Arabic language, with a specific focus on setting modern curricula and innovative teaching methods that would promote contemplative thinking.

1. Introduction

This research aims to complement and confirm the task that researchers have drawn earlier, in that it demonstrates the role of drama in the Arabic language teaching, and delineates its significant implications in refining the students' personality and in preparing them to possess tools of thinking along with means of problem solving.

These studies have followed a single process, being the experimental descriptive approach, due to its convergence in the implementation of the role play strategy, so as to highlight its impact on teaching the reading skill in the Arabic language. The motives behind choosing this topic include confirming the importance of changing the teaching methods, by balancing between traditional and modern strategies. In addition to proving the urgent need to use various methods in teaching the Arabic language in particular, in line with the learners' problems in reading, writing or listening.

However, it is worth noting that other studies also followed this process, yet with some differences in the researchers' approach in dealing with the role-play strategy in teaching Arabic language skills. To say it differently, researchers' earlier paradigms happen to differ in the nature of the language skill applied in their studies, among which we mention:

The effect of using the role-play method on developing contemplative thinking for third-graders, by Gehan Ahmed - Master Thesis - Islamic University of Gaza.

- The effect of using a single educational unit on two strategies, I.e. storytelling and role-playing, in developing

creative thinking among kindergarteners, by Muhammad Faramawi - Helwan University. In expectation of benefitting from the previous studies without redundancy, this study aims to follow the path of earlier studies, yet desires to be distinguished from them as there is almost no lesson in our curriculum which does not apply the skill of reading, whether silent, or loud...

In most of the studies, researchers question the extent of the feasibility of applying certain language teaching methods to the curricula. Most of the students, undoubtedly, suffer from acquiring their mother language in its accurate and eloquent forms. Furthermore, there are dangerous statistics about the numbers of students who face problems reading, writing, or even using the language correctly in thinking. This paper deals with an important method in teaching the reading skill in Arabic as it offers:

First: To examine the efforts put by Western and Arab scholars in describing the rules of the role-play strategy. Second: The most important step in the effort exerted in this paper is to reformulate the scholars' results impractical down to ground and applicable ways. The research paper deals with the descriptive aspects of "drama" with relation to role-playing and reading, by virtue of indicating its definition, and highlighting its pros and cons, along with delineating its implementation mechanisms.

Third: The statistical analysis has the most prominent effect in proving the credibility of the theoretical data, and cutting doubt about the certainty of the effectiveness of role play strategy. The latter was applied to two groups of students of second graders in one of the primary schools in the capital Abu Dhabi, through a contemplative thinking test. With this regard, statistics proved first, the validity of the results obtained from the theoretical hypotheses, second, the students' desperate need to diversify teaching methods, especially their ability to understand and represent texts increased by virtue of Role playing.

This study goes on the experimental descriptive approach, due to its aspect of neutralizing the researcher, leaving the opportunity for numbers, instead, to unveil facts. Consequently, this approach has proven its importance and strength in both linguistic research and teaching methods, in contemporary linguistic studies. As for the computer program, the study makes use of the "Excel" tables, however, the latter could not all be considered in the present paper due to the limited page numbers.

The analysis is applied to a sample of students in a school in Abu Dhabi, the capital of the UAE, by means of adopting a contemplative thinking test to two groups i.e. control and experimental. The implementation is based upon a unit of study which regarded several lessons that encompass dialogues, requiring thereby the participation of the largest possible number of students. This paper eventually, comes out with accurate statistics that reinforce the descriptive data that goes hand in hand with it.

The research paper has benefited from a set of sources and references, including: Lectures on Methods and Means of Teaching Islamic Education by Daoud Darwi. *The Foundations of Building curricula and their Organizations* by Hilmi Ahmed. *The Role of Playing in Developing Some Personal Aspects of a Pre-primary School Child* by Ahmed El-Shafei. *The Effect of Using the Role-playing Method on Developing Contemplative Thinking for Third-graders* by Jehan Ahmed and others.

The motive of indulging drama in educational curricula is to offer real educational opportunities and situations where both of students and teachers participate. This, in turn, stimulates their thinking and encourages group work on the basis of respect and mutual appreciation, with no need for sanctions. It moreover, strengthens the learners' self-evaluation and self-improvement.

The strategies of drama in education are many and varied, including protective strategies, and basic strategies such as: role-playing, framing, static images, the role of the expert and improvisation, storytelling and representation, and finally role-playing. The latter is a purposeful educational activity, based on the child's performance of a role other than who he really is, examples may include the roles of teachers, fathers or elder brothers. Accordingly, students represent different situations most of which are problems that require resolutions.

In these interactive activities, students are not assigned to accurately assume the role they plays, as they would be required to at later stages, they rather focus on bodily gestures and language, so as to perform the role that would serve them in the society and the environment.

Role playing is one of the most effective activities used as a tool for teaching educational data such as: Islamic education or social and national educations. To put it explicitly, playing roles of religious or historical figures, in plays, tales, short stories, wars and battles can boost students' abilities to measure and evaluate, it furthermore enhances them towards research, problem solving, and behavior observation.

Role play domains of use:

role play strategy is used in many areas, including:

- 1- Diagnosis and evaluation, such as: Diagnosing the role of the principals, teachers, physicians, sellers, drivers, farmers, merchants, grocers and carpenters.
- 2- Addressing students' behavioral issues.
- 3- All research fields, especially health education, social education, Islamic education and the Arabic language.
- 4- Competition areas that provide benefits to others and serve them.

5- Family related issues, taking into account reciprocal respect and possible disputes.

Role

play:

The term "role play science" denotes the automatic representation of situations that involve human relationships. This theory aims to reach the appropriate limit of realism in the educational process, which explains why it is sometimes referred to as the "characters' reincarnation", or "the representative play" (Helles, (2008)), for it goes pretty much like the representation of literary, artistic or medical personalities ...

As a matter of fact, many educational theories flourished in the West with realistic aspects, albeit a thorough look into their roots, reveals attempts by Arab scholars, who founded general features for many theories, as revealed in the holy verse "**He said, "O Adam, inform them of their names." And when he had informed them of their names, He said, "Did I not tell you that I know the unseen of the heavens and the earth? And I know what you reveal and what you have concealed."**"(Surat Al-Baqarah, Verse33). The verse, indeed, unveils that God has taught Adam all the names. The prophet, in his turn, became a tutor himself. In reality there are many verses and Hadiths which prove that this theory has ancient roots, however, this is not within the interest of this paper.

This term "Role" is derived from the Latin word "Rol7", which refers to the script on which the actor's role is written. Many human sciences by nature overlap with one another, hence, no scientific principles are set apart from philosophical consideration. With this regard, the reciprocal and reflexive influence that Arabic language has with Islam cannot be denied, nor can the influence of philosophy on linguistics and on sciences in general. The term "role" in was embedded in social sciences during the thirties of the previous century, thanks to scholars like Linton, Mead, and Moreno. (Obaid, William, and others, 2002)

The role is of three types (Al-Hassan, 2000):

-The psycho dramatic role: It includes roles with psychological characteristics.

- The physical role: it includes roles with physical characteristics.

-The social role: It includes roles having to do with the general professions that exist in society.

Like any scientific term, there are many definitions that arise around the term role, often converging in the general basic essence, but differing in the specific aspects that each scholar attempts to bring to light. In relation to this, Al-Shafi, states in his book "*The Role of Play in the Development of Certain Aspects of a Child's Personality*" that role play is a practical manner, which enables learners to solve problems, through the reincarnation of a specific personality (Al-Shafi'i, 2000). As for Atef Zaghoul, he has it that play role necessitates the performance of two or more individuals who will share dialogues that stem from

reality (Zaghoul, 2003). Besides, Zaghoul focused on the issue of the students' feelings, stating that students should not perform according to their emotions, they should, rather be directed to abide by the written scripts.

Majid Zaki Al-Jallad takes a similar stance with the previous definition. Nevertheless, he focuses on the issue of the criticism of students performance until the circle of role play benefit is complete (Al-Jallad, 2005). Afaneh however, believes that role play is an activity of performing educational plays, whereby students perform situations and activities through patterns committed to memorizing the text in advance, thereby, the teacher's role is to prepare the learners.

(Afaneh,2002)

In fact, the definitions are many, yet it is noticed that they all include elements like presence of personalities, texts, supervisors, audience, and critics. Except that each researcher focuses on no more than one aspect at a time. To pursue this idea, some scholars assume that the teacher's role is the most prominent detail; others would claim that the student's feeling is the main element. we believe that we cannot blink an element, or focus on another, for all the previous elements are of great importance in insuring the success of the role play process.

Psychological behavior has a great impact on the child's personality, as he determines his positions based on feelings that result from specific situations. This is what Levin went to by claiming that role play helps to reveal the problems that the child faces. The psychologist (Sigmund Freud) has also confirmed this belief, explaining that human beings are affected by the happy and sad psychological state (the slave, 2006). Therefore, characters reincarnation strategy favors the escape from the sad psychological state. (Piaget) has, as well, assumed that once the student perceives the acting elements, on the one hand, and the teacher plays the role of the supervisor, on the other hand, this would offer the learner the ability to adapt to the problems he might face. As for (Shaftek), he asserts that role-playing is a symptomatic reflex ion of the learner's mind, so by applying role play, he will reach a state of reconciliation with his reality.

From the foregoing, we deduce that role-play is of a great importance in encouraging the students' analytical spirit and in preparing them to deal with critical situations. Therefore, the reincarnation of a specific role results in a positive Impact on the students' psyche. Moreover, the acquisition of some social and ethical principles such as cooperation, patience, problem solving, and sacrifice ... can presumably be strengthened via role play technique. At this stage the importance of the supervisor lies in shedding light on corresponding role-play to society, in order to facilitate the retrieval of the situation when the students face a similar one in real life.

Among the benefits of role-play strategy is that it requires an interaction which encompasses the largest possible number of students. This, indeed, boosts the teacher to easily indulge them within the interaction. Due to the fact that role-play technique includes students with different abilities and ages, roles need to be carefully chosen and assigned to each student to guarantee the maximum benefit for all.

Rania Saasila indicates that some mental disorders such as shyness and aggressiveness in their simple form can be mitigated or treated through role-play (Saasil, 1998), so the student who performs a role with other classmates feels his integration within society. In other words, if the student senses that he is loved and influential, this effectively yields positive vibes to his psyche. This assumption is confirmed by many psychologists, mainly Freud.

One of the most important social values that role play promotes is the students' ability to develop the notion of fair competition with their classmates (Fahmy, 2001). Team work creates the suitable environment to enhance excellence and self confidence. It also supports the idea that the individual effort cannot provide an integrated work by itself, so there must be a group that works through it.

Role-play strategy goals

Since role-playing depends on the student's ability to improvise, it must be based on educational goals, the most important of which are:

- 1- Contribution to exposing the characteristics of desirable and unwanted behavior, such as the attitude of a miserly trader versus a generous child .
- 2- Exposition of the aspects of the topic and allowing the students to evaluate it.
- 3- Helping students to gain self-confidence, as they employ their linguistic, physical and intellectual skills.
- 4- Enriching linguistic use in a specific topic or issue.
- 5- Helping students to solve problems make decisions and develop their persuasion skills.
- 6- Helping them to train in many real life roles, through learning about multiple attitudes of human behavior patterns with different professions such as: the doctor's behavior in the clinic, the father's behavior at school and home.
- 7 - Discovering students' inclinations and desires, and then modifying and redirecting them according to what suits them most.
- 8- Helping students understand themselves and others.
- 9- Allowing them to discover their ability to recognize a specific situation.

- To keep in mind when using role play technique

According to al-Qurashi actors must understand the idea that their roles are specific, and that they are simulations of their reality (Al-Hailah 2002, p. 285). Perhaps if students perceive this point, they can truly benefit from the role-playing idea.

What must also be taken into account is the presence of a written scenario that sets out the general headlines of role representations. In fact, the scenario leads scholars to have two points of view. The first requires the presence of a text ready for students to study (Al-Hila Muhammad Mahmoud, 2002), and the second holds that students must contribute to the scenario, because they must be able to shift the problem from their minds into a written text. Nevertheless, we take the same stance of the first point of view, which has it that the presence of a written text is necessary; especially that it is written by specialized people, however, we also believe that the students behavioral presence in the text encourages them much. To be more explicit, students summoned for participation in writing the script are, undoubtedly, of an older age category, and here we are faced with the extent of the usefulness of role play technique with students in the preparatory and secondary levels.

The most important fields of role-play strategy:

The present day accelerated lifestyle has increased students' unfamiliar behavior, such as bullying and showing off. If we understand and identify the problem, and direct students towards role-playing, we shall notice that the effects of these problems have diminished. The efficiency of role-play does not stop in solving some bad behavioral manifestations at school, but rather exceeds to the family circle, differentiating between respect and disputes between parents and children (Al-Amawi, 2008). Accordingly, this method is used in teaching Arabic language, Islamic education, and national education.

Judging by the above, it is concluded that role play strategy helps students to retain events in their minds (Faramawi, 2001). Furthermore, the reincarnation of a certain personality not only helps to entrench the idea for a longer period, it also evokes it quickly if it matches a real situation.

Role-play, in fact, affects students' enthusiasm and avoids dullness. By doing so, it increases their concentration and ameliorates their levels. It is also an effective strategy in enhancing coordination between students, and creating an appropriate environment that encourages cooperation between them (Salah Al-Din Mahmoud, p. 401). The fact is that these strategies prove to be successful if applied to young aged categories

(below ten), because the latter at that age do not differentiate between reality and acting. In other words, students below age of ten merge role performance with real life. This can be justified by the misbehaviors and disputes that may characterize their classrooms in real life; therefore, the find comfort in the unreal role play environment thanks to the cooperation and respect it affords.

Jamal Al-Zaanain and Tayseer Nashwan indicate that role-play contributes to the education of people who need to move away from stereotypes in teaching children (Nashwan Tayseer et al., 2003). Stereotyping is not limited to school education, as parents may be able to implement it within a narrower framework with their children.

Depiction the implementation of role play strategy:

Some religious, political and artistic personalities may have a major impact on people's lives. This impact does not entail admiring them only, but rather exceeds to imitating their daily lifestyle such as food and clothing, and even imitating their physical manners, speech style, and way more. With this regard, role-play enables us to choose a successful character who reflects the good qualities and values we want to lay in students. By doing so, they will cling to these principles faster than with the typical way of education. Another portrait of role play, is the students reincarnation of real characters with less widespread topics, particularly at the primary level (Hillis, 2003). For example, the issue of drugs in schools is closer to the imagination of young students especially. The other way round is also true. As opposite to the previous one, having a real issue with real imaginary people is also applicable.

With regard to the environment, we must pay a special attention to the climate that offers a successful work atmosphere, due to the credibility it may afford. There is no doubt that the impact of the role play performance related to the influence of technology on the family is very important. The role play strategy can be more successful with the presence of representative tools like mobile phones, makeup and clothes, in addition to the participation of adult characters like parents. All of the former contribute to the success of the performance, and in reinforcing the students' excitement and attention.

Professor Soheir Mohamed Salama indicates that there are many tools that must be used, just like sleeping bags, tents and compasses for the camp, and like combs and creams for the barber (gauze, 2006)

Role-play

Drawbacks

Like all educational theories, role play strategy has negative aspects that show up during its implementation, and the transition from the unreal stage performance into reality is bound to a set of complex matters. The latter regard the students age and mental abilities, besides the supervisors experience in this field, in addition to the material capacity of the institution in creating the suitable environment, as well as the nature of the scenario presented

Perhaps the most important factor that should be available is a supervisor who has extensive experience, expertise and faith in conducting some educational activities such as role-play (Budair, 2007).

Savtel pointed at the need to pay attention to the issue of not adequately preparing students (Al-Jallad, 2005), who need first to acquire a complete idea about the subject, and this requires a well organized supervisor. One of the elements that hinder role-play from being an efficient strategy in communicating information and other values and principles, is the presence of a number of shy students. If supervisors do not find a way to integrate the latter, they will block its application.

Role-playing strategy implementation

For the purpose of implementing role-play, there are several steps that must be followed sequentially in order to achieve the best results. However, there is disagreement in the number of steps. Some scholars hold the belief that ten steps are necessary while others have it that eleven steps need to be followed, nevertheless, these two viewpoints do not correspond to this paper which follows Savtel pattern. Savtel refers to applying nine steps (Al-Jallad, 2005) which seems to be the most reasonable stand point, for no steps repetition is tolerated.

First: Identifying the dimensions of the problem to the students is compulsory, in the expectation of setting the topic to their perception, raising enthusiasm, and raising awareness about the importance of role-playing. Second: Analyzing roles and trying to align them with the characters that will represent them. At this point, it is the supervisor responsibility to choose the appropriate character for the suitable role to integrate the student with his role, which will, in turn, affect his psyche.

Third: We must prepare an appropriate environment where students represent roles, such as ensuring the availability of the necessary tools that make the performance sound real for them.

Fourth: Putting efforts in explaining the concept of role play, so as to enable students to understand it when exposed to it (Al-Amawi, 2008).

Fifth: Starting performance, which is the last step before evaluation. It represents the main phase that reveals the efficiency of the previous points.

Sixth: The objective of role-play will only be achieved through a comprehensive assessment of the work i.e. through a thorough analysis of the goals and the extent of their efficiency. Moreover, supervisors are requested to identify the students' errors.

Eighth: The teacher or supervisor must repeat the evaluation process after "reenactment", through involving students in the discussion of realistic solutions.

Ninth: Linking performance to reality, by relating acting to students' lives and experiences. By doing so, supervisors reach the target principles and goals, which they implicitly establish to the students perception (Executioner 2005).

Sections of role-play

As mentioned earlier, role-play strategy is one of the most important methods in education. It helps the establishment of some values like self-confidence, in addition to the easy communication of information apart from educational stereotypes. Role-play is divided into several sections based mainly on dialogue and performance. Professor Salah El-Din Mahmoud points at three sections (Arafa, 2006):

1. Acting based on a conversational script between two or more characters.
2. Storytelling, which does not necessarily entail dialogues.
3. Free acting based on the performance of a specific situation without the presence of a text, be it a dialogue or an anecdotal. This section, in fact, necessitates more experience and expertise than the first two parts.
4. The fourth type that can be added is silent performance. The previous types are bound to spoken language. It is, however, possible for students to represent a position using signs or body language only, without a need to verbal utterance. As a matter of fact, this type allows students with speech or hearing problems to participate without embarrassment.

Role play conditions

1- Students should be briefly introduced to the role-play process, along with its action plan, thus the following must be done:

A- Students should work in a group provided that each of them takes a role.
B- Supervisors should stop the role-play process when necessary, in order to benefit from feedback, and to open discussions on a specific point that is controversial.

A- The role-play process begins when learners reincarnate the role.

2- Playing roles should be set in a sophisticated and effective way to transfer information and preserve time. This method helps supervisors gain the students' trust and convince them of the work they do.

3- Supervisors must be serious and interested in role play strategy, in order to arouse students' attention and integrate them seriously in the presentation. The former must also accept students' ideas, respect and praise their opinions, and discuss issues that cannot be implemented during the role-play process.

4- Role-play strategy necessitates the appropriate circumstances, by virtue of which the supervisor is enabled to clarify the performance rules, with the aim of convincing students of their roles.

5- The process of choosing the role is an important procedure, and the teacher should decide what he wants of the role to be:

- Does he want it to be instructive?
- Does he want it to take the shape of advice?
- Does he want it to launch discussion and create dialogues?
- Does he want it to be educational?

6- Choosing the language used in the role-play process is an important matter that helps support the role and stimulates students' interest in it.

The researchers' view on reading has evolved throughout time. All efforts have been focused on the process of recognizing letters then pronouncing them. Therefore, researchers have always focused on the human organ's speech system including: the mouth with the tongue and the lips, opinions, later on, tended to assume that reading is a complicated process, in which a group of attributes need to be linked and inferred, taking into account the psychological state of the reader as well as the reading purpose ... subsequently, the issue of intellectual activity was also referred to as a means of problem solving and understanding reality (Al-Bajah, 2002)., Pp. 64-65).

The concept of reading evolved from being a mechanical process to being an intellectual activity (Spree, agonist, 2003). This activity requires understanding, comprehending, as well as evoking past situations and linking them to the present when need be.

Beyond the lexical definition of reading, Professor Ashour defines it as "a complicated, complex and hierarchical process related to thinking with its different layers, in that every thinking layer depends on what lies beneath, and cannot take place without it. As for the reading process, it is similar to all the educational operations performed by teachers" (Ratib and others, p. 64). His definition focuses on the issue of thinking and that reading is no longer a tool to access information.

Reading has also been defined as «a process of thinking, meaning that the individual is the one who determines his reading goals. On the basis of these goals, the effectiveness of reading, its speed, and its benefit are

determined" (Badawi, 2005). However, this definition blinks the fact that children do not have the ability to define their reading goals.

This research paper holds that reading is a complex process, in which the relationship between words is intertwined and influenced by the reader's mental capabilities. The latter are, indeed, dictated by the circumstances surrounding the reader.

As to transcend the many lexical definitions of reading, there is no doubt that it nourishes the mind and provides knowledge. In reality, many nations have developed and still develop thanks to reading. The latter became a habit for some nations because they believe that it is the most successful way to develop thought and to grant access to knowledge and science. It is also a means of intellectual communication between societies, either between the elite or the common people. Reading is also one of the most important means to interpret thoughts and express feelings (Zaqqout, 1999), for it is a window of the human thought.

Reading objectives in the foundation stage:

A child needs to enhance his linguistic baggage during the early school stage. Hence it is worth noting that at this level, reading is the most important way for the acquisition of new vocabulary and sentence structures. It also helps to formulate these structures easily and smoothly. Furthermore, reading has the capacity to enhance eloquence and fluency, particularity for the learners with pronunciation difficulties, especially if trained to read ancient poetry or prose texts or the holy Quran. These texts offer the accurate structure of sentences with sound pronunciation signs, which correspond to the learners needs in the early stages. Through reading, the student can be drilled on punctuation, like knowing how to end a specific idea using the appropriate intonation ... indeed, no two disagree on the importance of knowledge acquisition in developing students experiences and helping him to face real life situations. Accordingly, the more the student's knowledge increases thanks to reading, the more his learning desire increases as well. Last but not least, reading develops some skills like silent and loud readings (Radwan 2002)

Reading sections

Reading is divided into several sections, some of which are related to reading goals, such as quick reading, accomplishable reading and aggregative reading (Al-Bajah 2002, p. 74). Some of these goals are bound to mental and intellectual predispositions, such as a mandatory reading. The latter is a type of reading based on the achievement of a specific goal assigned to the reader, such as reading lessons. Nevertheless, the benefits of this reading tend unfortunately, to be easily forgotten. This can be attributed to the readers' uninterest in text he is compelled to read, hence once the reading goal is attained, the information quickly disappears.

Another type of reading is reading for pleasure, which has long term effects because it stems from curiosity for knowledge. In this regard, professor (Elijah) indicates that readers seek recourse to it to, so as to escape the concerns and trouble of real life (Al-Beja 2002, p. 74).

The reading is also divided into loud reading and silent reading. The latter does not entail moving the lips, as Professor Al-Dulaimi explains that it should be within the mind far from external conditions (Al-Dulaimi et al. 2003).

Silent reading aims to familiarize the reader with quick understanding and strong observation (Ashour and others. 2003). It is also a good way to meditate and to drill the mind on the matching skill and the use of imagination. Some scholars hold it this type of reading is more credible and efficient than the aloud one (Darwish, p. 108 Ashour and others. 2003).

Nevertheless, one of the silent reading drawbacks is the impossibility to correct reading mistakes, which is sufficient evidence that it is not appropriate for primary classes, nor for low grading students, nor students with speech difficulties. Let alone the fact that it sets a barrier between the reader and the audience, depriving the reader, thus from fluency and eloquence.

Contrarily to silent reading, the loud one is attained by means of releasing the sound through the lips. This type of reading is credited for its ability to develop the readers' rhetoric. It moreover, enables them to benefit from pronunciation, grammatical and punctuality corrections

As mentioned earlier, loud reading requires more time than does the silent one. Al-Waeli indicates that it limits readers' freedom (Al-Wakeel and others (2005)). In addition to the fact that it orients the focus on the reader alone, which might cause his classmates to lose interest and get preoccupied with other issues. Not to mention the teachers desperate efforts to focus on the students reading, especially if they encounter speech difficulties, or if they are numerous.

Reading in terms of its purpose may be divided into:

Quick reading is common in the cases of understanding general ideas, or remembering subjects, or checking specific words and phrases.

- A Reading that devotes itself to extended topics, such as reading reports and research. Meditative reading it is a reading that needs to be considered carefully, as readers, through it, take notes, examine details and discuss them.

- Reading for criticism (Al-Hassan, 2000), it enables judgments and opinions to be adopted regarding the text. This reading necessitates quick intuition in linking topics.

Some students may experience difficulty in reading data that is outside the curriculum, such as reading a newspaper, or a prose or a poetry text. The difficulty, actually lays in the complex vocabulary and the writing style that go beyond the level of the scheduled book. Thence, there must be an experienced and well practiced teacher who manages to deal with cases, like stimulating loud reading to slightly difficult texts, with rewards in return.

Institutions also play an important role in carrying out procedural studies on samples of their students. This procedure is compulsory in order to identify the students' weaknesses, and to try, consequently, to find a system of their own to solve these problems, particularly by providing teachers with the necessary tools and means.

All efforts must be put to help students read (Furah, 2003). The library, for instance, has an important role in providing the appropriate books of the most recent publications that are pertinent to the students' level. Parents at home, as well, are extremely enticed to encourage their children, by assigning them to some readings with occasional rewards in return.

Reinforcing or hindering reading:

The most prominent thing in this regard is the established curriculum. In other words, The nature of the chosen texts stands as a real challenge to the student's knowledge development, Hence authors must provide texts that contain familiar words, in addition to the element of suspense and the link with reality.

Furthermore, the method of discussing these texts must be taken into consideration. The students' positive opinion aspects, for instance, should be respected, especially in primary stages to avoid backlash. The teachers, as well, must direct his pupils to questions that need research and study, whether through schools available resources such as the library, discussion sessions, or at home. It is a method that is, in essence, based on research, information collection, analysis, and the balance between them to prepare them for class discussion. The latter offers each colleague to get acquainted with the data and research established by his classmates, which gets all the students to participate in preparing the lesson.

The teacher per se, is one of the most important factors that affect reading (Al-Amawi, 2008). He must contribute to enabling children and adults to perceive many dimensions in their world and gain new concepts, by establishing good communication with them. A teacher is compelled to raise a generation sincerely; hence he must not fail to engrave values and morals in his students' hearts.

Things leading to reading errors:

The teacher must identify the words that the student has a repetitive inability in uttering them. This can be explained in a set of serious reasons, such as eye movement disorder, lack of linguistic options, or inability to understand the text. In fact, teachers can avoid reading errors by choosing reading material that suits the students' level, or by increasing their linguistic vocabulary, and clarifying the text's meanings. In addition to taking into consideration the educational data that responds to their inclinations, and satisfy their needs. All of the previous can eventually help them to master reading.

The error may arise from placing a letter elsewhere, as in: (fogrive) instead of forgive. What helps overcome these errors is the easiness of the text which enables students to read the words in one context. It is necessary to pay attention to the text chosen, for it must be of big font. In addition to that, language must be familiar and uncomplicated, with few metaphors and similes (Abdel Hamid (2006)).

Practical application

This paper is based on two approaches, the first of which is descriptive, which represents the theoretical data for role play strategy and the reading skill. The second approach is experimental and based on the impact of role-play strategy on reading in the Arabic language. Accordingly, the population of the study comprises students in the second primary class in a school in Abu Dhabi In the United Arab Emirates. The idea of experimentation is based on two main steps:

First: A contemplative thinking test with two classes of the same level. It has been applied to a unit of study consisting of three texts, each of which includes twenty questions.

Second: role-play strategy was applied to one of the two classes. Afterwards, the contemplative test is applied to the students of that class. The credibility of the test is confirmed by the half-split, where the stability factor is up to (69%).

The study sample:

As already stated, the population concerns second primary class students at Al-Najah School in Abu Dhabi, and the sample consists of two classes which consists each of 28 students equally. The duration of the role-play process for the unit chosen, lasted seven semesters.

First study hypothesis feedback results:

The first hypothesis of the study states the absence of differences of statistical significance at the level of 0.05, the average score of the experimental group students and the average of their peers is in significance. The control group is significant in the reflective thinking test due to the use of the role-play method. To verify the credibility of this research, "T. test independent sample" is used.

The following table clarifies this:

Table 1 Test results

Axis /Group /Average/ Number/ Standard deviation/ Value T /Significance Value Significance level

Meditation Experimental

Control-And obser

Vation

Conclusion Experimental Function at 0,01

Control

Expected Experimental

Skills Control

Interpretation Experimental

Control

Final Experimental Function at 0,01

Grade Control

The tabular "T" value is a of free degree (201) and at the significance level (= (0.051.98) The tabular "T" value is a of free degree (201) and has a significance level of 0.02 = 2.55 It is clear from the previous table that the calculated value of "T" is greater than the tabular value of "T" at the significance level of 0.02

This means that there are statistical differences between the two groups: the experimental and the control. This is evident in the final results of the contemplative test, which were in favor of the experimental group. Using the following equation: "η With regard to the intensity of the effect, the researcher calculates the Eta square" n2

$$N2 = t2 / t2 + df$$

Table 2 Effect measure for control and experimental groups

Axis	Value T	Eta square	Influence
Meditation and deduction	4.521	0.091	Medium
deduction	5.812	0,151	Big
Proposed solutions	3.610	0.07	Medium
Interpretation	3.517	0,085	little
Final grade	5.901	0.151	Big

The effect of role-play method on the experimental group has a significant impact on the second level and on the overall score; on the other hand, the mean effect was relevant to the skill of the proposed solutions. However, it has little effect on the skill of interpretation.

Role-play application in its successful form, thanks to the supervisors, has a clear impact on the experimental group, so it is noted that students' concentration and observation was greater, besides enthusiasm, facial expressions and body language were the most prominent elements in their performances compared to the control group. As a result their passion to hear from others increased too. Therefore it can be said that role-play increased the experimental group students understanding and acquisition to the present data with the ability to retrieve if when need be.

This in fact confirms the validity of this method, and confirms previous studies in this field such as Fahmi's study (2001) and Jaballah's study (2001) In addition to other studies that have affected teaching

methods, and made them more effective and influential for students. This study indeed shows the difference between the use of traditional method and modern ones in improving the students' performance. Not only in terms of achievement and obtaining certificates, but also at the level of their personalities in real life, so as to be positive participants in society.

Findings and further recommendations

Several studies have been conducted in the field of teaching methods and educational sciences, ending up with numerous results and opinions. However, one common objective brings them all together, which is the advancement of the educational process and the production of a healthy, conscious and clever generation in the Arab world. Autonomous responsible generations of individuals who manage problem solving, establish a strong prosperous society, and link knowledge to real life situations at any age.

In fact, we cannot produce clever students except if we possess an applicable curriculum, in addition to the presence of teachers who are ready to apply the recommendations that result from these studies. Hence, it is high time institutions collected this huge amount of valuable studies and adopted them in school curricula for the benefit of students.

This study recommends generalizing role-play strategy in all Arabic language skills, including: reading, writing, and listening. It is highly recommended to make it one of the main teaching methods. However, it is worth noting that teaching methods and means should be diversified. In other words, educational institutions should not limit themselves to traditional methods only, although the latter have undoubtedly served the greatest scholars and researchers.

Role-play strategy is special because it releases students from boredom during the teaching session, by so the students lack of focus decreases, and they are more likely to interact with the teacher and the lesson. Drama and acting play a prominent role in developing the skill of contemplative thinking and this meets with the students' needs and inclinations.

Eventually, the study recommends the establishment of programs and workshops that train teachers to possess the tools of role play skill application, until all its dimensions are understood, and all its details are made clear. They should also be trained to deal with the problems that may face them in the application process, and should also be endowed with the necessary means to enhance the implementation of this strategy.

Reference

- Abdul Hameed, Hebham Mohammed (2006): *Children's Lyrical, Kinetic, Cultural, Inspirational, Popular, Educational, and Dramatic Games*, Amman, Al-Safa House for Distribution and Publishing.
- Afaneh, Izzo Ismail, Al-Louh Ahmed Hassan (2008). *Teaching theater theater modern vision in class learning*, Amman, Jordan, Dar Al-Masirah for publishing and distribution.
- Afaneh, Lulu (2002). *Level of autistic thinking skills, field training problems, students of the Faculty of Education at the Islamic University - College of Education, Gaza - Palestine*.
- Al-Abr, Shirinyehia (2006). *Language Sciences*, Cairo, Dargharib.
- Al-Bajah, Abdel-Fattah (2002): *Teaching Children Literacy and Writing Skills*, Amman, Jordan, Dar Al-Fikr, Publishing and Distribution.
- Al-Dulaimi, Taha Hussein, Al-Waeli, Suad Abdul Karim Abbas (2005): *The Arabic Language Curriculum and Methods of its Teaching*, Amman - Jordan, Dar Al-Shorouk.
- Al-Dulaimi, Taha Hussein, Al-Waeli, Suad Abdel Karim Abbas (2003): *Methods of Operation in Teaching Arabic Language*, Amman - Jordan, Dar Al-Shorouk.
- Al-Dulaimi, Hussein Alita, Al-Waeli, Suad Abd Al-Karim (2005), *Modern trends in teaching Arabic*, Irbid - Jordan, the world of modern books
- Al-Hailah, Muhammad Mahmoud (2002). *Educational games and production techniques, psychology, education, and science*, Dar Al-Masara, Amman, Jordan.
- Al-Hailah, Mahmoud Muhammad (2002). *Educational Technology for the Development of Thinking and Speech and Practice*, Amman, Jordan, Dar Al-Massara.
- Al-Hassan, Hisham (2000), *I knocked on teaching children to read and write*, Amman, Jordan, Dar Al-Masirah.
- Al-Hassan, Hisham (2000): *I taught children to read and write*, Amman - Jordan, Dar Al-Masirah.
- Al-Jallad, Majdzaki (2005) *Learn values and teach them a conceptual theory and apply methods and strategies for teaching values*, 2nd floor, Amman, Jordan, Dar Al-Masirah.
- Al-Shafei, Ahmed Abdel-Hamid, Khodr, Salah Hassan (2000). *The role of playing in the development of some aspects of the personality of a pre-primary school child*, the College of Education, Al-Azhar University, the Journal of Education.
- Al-Wakeel, Helmy Ahmed, Singer Amin Ahmed (2005): *bases of Building and Organizing curricula*, Amman - Jordan, Dar Al-Masirah.

- Arafa, Mahmoud Salah El-Din (2006). *Boundaries of thinking, contemporary educational visions in teaching thinking and learning*, Cairo, the world of books.
- Ashour, Ratib, Abu Al-Hija ', Abdel-Rahim (2003):*The curriculum Between Theory and Practice*, Amman, Dar Al-Masirah.
- Ashour, Ratib Kassem, Al-Hawamdeh, Mohammed Fouad (2003):*Methods of Teaching Arabic Language Between Theory and Practice*, Amman - Jordan, Dar Al-Masarra.
- Badawi, Mustafa Riyadh (2005):*The Problems of Reading from Childhood to Adolescence Diagnosis and Treatment*, Amman-Jordan, Dar Al-Safaa.
- Badir, Kariman Muhammad (2007):*Active Learning*, Amman, Jordan, Dar Al Masirah for Publishing and Distribution.
- Badir, Kariman, Sadiq, and Emily (2000):*Developing children's linguistic skills*, Cairo, the world of books.
- Badir, Kariman (2006): *Positive Learning and Learning Difficultie, a modern Psycho-Educational, view*, Egypt, Cairo, Books World.
- Fahmy, Ehsan, Abdul Rahim (2001). *The effectiveness of using the playgrounds to collect third-graders to prepare grammatical rules and their attitudes towards it* "The Reading and Knowledge Magazine, Ninth Issue, College of Education, University of Ain Shams.
- Faramawy, Mohammed (2001). *The effect of using an educational unit onst story Telling, and role-play strategies in developing for kindergarteners* , Cairo University 4 College of Education, Helwan University.
- Fourah, Nahedh Sa`id (2003):*The effectiveness of a proposed program to address some difficulties in learning to read for pupils in the elementary stage in Gaza*, unpublished thesis, College of Education, Gaza, Palestine.
- Hillis, Daudderwish. (2008) *Lectures in Methods of Teaching Islamic Education*, 2nd edition, Gaza - Palestine, Afak for printing and publishing.
- Hillis, Mahasad Salim (2003):*The influence of the Dramatic experience Method in Improving the Spelling Levels and Direction Toward Parents, sixth grade students*, master's unpublished thesis, College of Education, Gaza - Palestine.
- Mahmoud, Salah Al-Din Arafa (2006): *Unlimited Thinking, Contemporary Educational Visions in Teaching and Learning Thinking*, Cairo, The World of Books.
- Nashwan, Tayseer, Al-Zaanain, Jamal (2003): *Teaching and Learning Techniques*, Gaza-Palestine, University Student Library.
- Obaid, William, Afaneh, Izzo (2002). *Thinking and School Curriculum*, Kuwait, Al Falah Library.
- Radwan, Mounir Muhammad Radwan (2002):*The effect of Using the Partial Method in Teaching Reading on Developing its Skills in the First Basic Class*, Unpublished dissertation, Al-Aqsa University, Gaza.
- Saasila, Rania (1998). *The effectiveness of the Role-Play Method in Teaching Social Experiences for Kindergarteners*, College of Education, University Journal, Damascus, Humanities and Education, Article 41, No. 4
- Shash, Suhair Muhammad Salamah (2006):*Psychology of Language*, Cairo, Zahraa Al Sharq Library.
- The holy Quran
- Zaghloul, Atef Hamed (2003). *The effectiveness of Simulation Using Computers in Developing Scientific Concepts Among Kindergarteners*, Cairo, the Egyptian Association for Scientific Education, 7th conference, M1, Faculty of Education, Ain Shams University.
- Zaqqout, Muhammad Shahatha (1999): *The Mentor in Teaching Arabic Language*, 2nd floor, Gaza, Afaq Library.

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